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Abstract: Deliverable 6.13 is a follow-up report on the SSH Training Community organised by SSHOC Task 6.4 within the duration of the SSHOC project. It sets out to demonstrate and describe the activities that built the SSH Training Community.

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Executive Summary

The SSH Training Community is an important part of the engagement and training activities in the *Social Sciences and Humanities Open Cloud* (SSHOC) project. The concerted efforts of the SSHOC Task 6.4 lead to the development of the SSH Training Community which is a compilation of formats and tools that foster community building and engagement, mutual learning, and networking among stakeholders involved in training activities related to the Social Sciences and Humanities (SSH).

Through building expertise and empowering its network, the SSHOC T6.4 aims to provide the SSH community of trainers with the necessary knowledge, skills, and expertise required to use and contribute to SSHOC resources. This deliverable is a follow-up report of the D6.10 *Report on the SSHOC Training Community*¹ on the activities of Task 6.4 in the SSHOC project. It provides an update on the developments and reports on the overall efforts and implementation towards building a community for trainers in the SSH.

The Training Community was launched in September 2019. Its overarching goal of knowledge acquisition and networking among stakeholders in the SSH has two main components. First, facilitating knowledge exchange and collaboration between trainers in the field of SSH. Therefore, the train-the-trainer approach which aims at empowering trainers and creating multipliers in support of open science in SSH was applied. In addition, a bottom-up approach is used in the SSH Training Community, and processes and tools were adapted to the Training Community members' needs. Second, building expertise on tools and services offered by the SSH Open Marketplace. Two databases have been set within the T6.4, thus supporting data sharing in the SSH: The Training Discovery Toolkit² and the Trainers Directory³.

The first *Report on the SSHOC Training Community* (D6.10, published in May 2020) was focused on the community building development process, whereas D6.13 aims to illustrate results and puts a special emphasis on sustainability of the SSH Training Community once the project ends (April 2022).

¹ SSHOC D6.10 *Report on the SSHOC Training Community*: <https://zenodo.org/record/4558301#.YWA7T2LP2Mq> [accessed Nov 2021].

² Link to the *SSH Training Discovery Toolkit*: https://training-toolkit.sshopencloud.eu/entities?search=&f%5B0%5D=content_type%3Asource [accessed Nov 2021].

³ Link to the SSH Trainers Directory: <https://sshopencloud.eu/trainers-directory> [accessed Nov 2021].

Abbreviations and Acronyms

CESSDA	Consortium of European Social Sciences Data Archives
CLARIN	Common Language Resources and Technology Infrastructure
DANS	Dutch National Centre of Expertise and Repository for Research Data
DARIAH	The Digital Research Infrastructure for the Arts and Humanities
EOSC	European Open Science Cloud
FAIR data	Data that is Findable, Accessible, Interoperable and Reusable
FOSTER	Facilitate Open Science Training for European Research
GDPR	General Data Protection Regulation
GESIS	GESIS - Leibniz Institute for the Social Sciences
IASSIST	International Association for Social Science Information Service and Technology
LIBER	Ligue des Bibliothèques Européennes de Recherche – Association of European Research Libraries
OpenAIRE	Open Access Infrastructure for Research in Europe
RDM	Research Data Management
SSH	Social Sciences and Humanities
SSHOC	Social Sciences and Humanities Open Cloud
WP	Work Package

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1. Introduction

The SSH Training Community is a key deliverable of the SSHOC project that builds the Social Sciences and Humanities (SSH) part of the European Open Science Cloud (EOSC). As an activity under Work Package 6 (Fostering Communities, Empowering Users & Building Expertise), Task 6.4 established and continues to build and empower the SSH Training Community—a compilation of formats and tools that foster community engagement, mutual learning, and networking among stakeholders in the SSH. Currently, as of November 2021, the Training Community consists of 172 members covering all disciplines in the Social Sciences and Humanities. The formal activities of the SSH Training Community under the SSHOC project will continue until the end of the SSHOC project (April 2022).

The core goal of the Training Community is to facilitate knowledge exchange and collaboration between stakeholders in training in the SSH on tools and services, with the aim of developing a data-sharing culture following the FAIR principles in open science. Therefore, the various knowledge exchange and collaboration formats have been developed, like monthly Training Community Calls. Due to the COVID-19 pandemic, all events have so far taken place online. Moreover, the Training Community contains the Trainers Directory⁴, which is a database of trainers in the SSH. Next to the Training Discovery Toolkit⁵ (see D6.11), the Trainers Directory supports the ambitions of the T6.4 in establishing resources for train-the-trainer activities. The Training Community, thus, builds new expertise and at the same time draws on existing knowledge and capacities that are already present within the SSHOC partner network.

This document builds upon the first report on the SSH Training Community (D6.10 *Report on the SSHOC Training Community*⁶) which focused primarily on the concept of the Training Community: current plans, future activities, and interaction with members. As an extension of the first report, D6.13 elaborates on the results of the manifold SSH Training Community activities. It describes the SSH Training Community Strategy (chapter two) and illustrates the Training Community in detail with a special focus on feedback from Training Community members (chapter three). After portraying the Trainers Directory (chapter four), the report highlights future plans on how to make the SSH Training Community sustainable once the SSHOC project ends (chapter five).

⁴ Link to the SSH Trainers Directory: <https://sshopencloud.eu/trainers-directory> [accessed Nov 2021].

⁵ Link to the SSH Training Discovery Toolkit: https://training-toolkit.sshopencloud.eu/entities?search=&f%5B0%5D=content_type%3Asource [accessed Nov 2021].

⁶ SSHOC D6.10 *Report on the SSHOC Training Community*: <https://zenodo.org/record/4558301#.YWA7T2LP2Mq> [accessed Nov 2021].

2. The SSH Training Community Strategy

2.1 Objectives

As pointed out in the *SSHOC Community Engagement Strategy*⁷ (D6.1) and followed-up by the *SSHOC Building Expertise Strategy* (D6.2), the SSH Training Community is an important part of the SSHOC outreach activities. To successfully build the SSH part of EOSC, it is crucial to foster community engagement of end users like researchers, associations, intermediaries, and other stakeholders in the SSHOC environment.

Community involvement stands at the centre of the SSH Training Community activities. Providing the community of trainers with knowledge and skills is crucial to empower the SSHOC network and to build expertise among SSH stakeholders. Implemented activities are aimed to equip the community with knowledge so it can contribute to open science practices in the EU, empower it to adhere and stick to FAIR principles, and build a strong network of skilled users and trainers to act as multipliers in order to maximise the impact of the SSH open cloud infrastructure.

Committing SSHOC users to principles of open science, giving them theoretical and practical knowledge of tools and services in the cloud and connecting stakeholders from all over the EU is a complex process. To realise these ambitious goals and establish the SSH Training Community as a valuable platform for the promotion and uptake of the SSHOC outputs while fostering a network of SSH trainers, a threefold approach has been followed. Regular activities that combine the three below-mentioned elements of the strategy will be outlined in the [next sub-chapter \(chapter 2.2\)](#).

1. Knowledge transfer and exchange: Building knowledge, skills and expertise

One main element of the SSH Training Community strategy is user empowerment. By equipping the community members/trainers with knowledge, skills, and expertise, they can benefit from and contribute to SSHOC resources.

“The core goal of SSHOC training activities is to share knowledge so that SSHOC user communities can make use of SSHOC services, tools and data throughout the research lifecycle and according to the FAIR principles by improving related skills, knowledge and competencies.”⁸

⁷ See *SSHOC Community Engagement Strategy*: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.3592244> [accessed Nov 2021].

⁸ See *SSHOC Building Expertise Strategy*, p. 8: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4558294> [accessed Nov 2021].

However, the SSH Training Community is more than mere knowledge transfer: via interactive formats, there is an ongoing exchange process on best practices, innovative tools and services that are offered within SSHOC and its partners network.

2. Building a strong European network of diverse stakeholders engaged in the SSH

As the SSH are composed of a highly diverse variety of academic disciplines, the SSHOC project benefits from an enormous range of expertise. Fostering networking and collaboration between those experts/trainers and between the experts/trainers and the SSHOC project ensures active involvement of relevant communities in the shaping of the SSH Open Cloud. Ultimately, these interactions help everyone in the SSH communities, because contributing to the project outputs helps shaping the SSHOC tools and services based on the communities' needs.

3. Contributing to open science practices in the EU

Committing to open science practices (e.g., to FAIR data) is crucial to the whole SSHOC project and consequently, for the organisation of the SSH Training Community. That means encouraging a data-sharing culture e.g., by organising events, sharing best practices on data sharing and open science, and making training materials that are produced and used for these events available for reuse free of charge.⁹

2.2 Methodology and Organisation of the SSH Training Community

The impact of the COVID-19 pandemic

In order to maximise results, WP6 has chosen diverse types of activities and means of communication to effectively build and support the SSH Training Community within a wide disciplinary and geographic range. The COVID-19 pandemic reshaped major parts of the community activities. Consequently, original plans to enable live interactions within the community had to be amended: all activities took place online. For example, the SSHOC train-the-trainer bootcamps could not be held on-site and within a brief period, they were organised as fully virtual encounters.¹⁰ The T6.4 activities were quickly adapted to the new situation. All interaction was shifted to virtual environments and delivered online via online events,

⁹ Zenodo website: [SSHOC Community Engagement Strategy](#) [accessed Nov 2021].

¹⁰ For more information on the online SSHOC train-the-trainer bootcamps, see D6.12 <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5734300> [accessed Nov 2021].

meetings, and emails, while adjusting the formats to offer as much interaction as possible, to support the community of trainers in the SSH and to keep them engaged.

An ongoing learning process

The organisation of the SSH Training Community has been a continuous learning process during the whole project lifecycle: It has been crucial to understand what the community's needs are, and how to best tailor the SSHOC tools and services accordingly. For example, active user/trainer involvement in the development of SSHOC tools such as the SSH Training Discovery Toolkit (via feedback loops) induced user experiences incorporation, reflection on work within the Task, and adjustment of the development and implementation by using a bottom-up approach. The training options made available to the Training Community members are based on their needs, following consultation. Due to the pandemic, online event formats became the new standard and thus, the needs of trainers in the community changed. The T6.4 activities were adapted to the new circumstances at a quick pace and therefore, sharing of knowledge on online event formats with the whole Training Community was enabled.

Membership

There is a dedicated page on the SSHOC website for training, including the Training Community. Trainers can join the network by signing up via <https://www.sshopencloud.eu/join-ssh-training-community>. The trainers who sign up are added to the Training Community mailing list through which information about events and other news is distributed. Members also receive access to an online platform where materials from the Training Community Calls are shared.

The train-the-trainer approach

The train-the-trainer approach is the overarching principle of the SSH Training Community methodology. Supporting trainers to improve their skills in training other trainers requires teaching of the best possible ways to deliver topic-specific training materials and expertise.¹¹ Training participants serve as knowledge multipliers who pass on the knowledge gained in the SSHOC events. Providing high quality training is not only important to educate the trainers that attend the SSHOC events directly, but also for overall promotion and visibility of the EOSC and the SSHOC project and related resources. Ultimately, trained participants can increase the overall impact of open science efforts in the EU. Knowledge transfer at international and institutional levels is equally relevant for the project duration and beyond. To best enable trained participants in their role as multipliers, a solid mix of theory and practice proved to be

¹¹ To see how the train-the-trainers approach was implemented in the *SSHOC Train-the-Trainer Bootcamps*, see D6.12 *Report on the Train-The-Trainer Bootcamps*: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5734300> [accessed Nov 2021].

useful. The train-the-trainer approach allowed the SSHOC T6.4 team to use a variety of training methods and activities, as follows:

Training methods

The following training methods are used:

Presentations

Presentations constitute the didactic foundation of the training activities executed by SSHOC T6.4. It is important to give the participants a substantial knowledge basis so that they get the theoretical input that is necessary to gain a solid understanding of the presented topic.

Group work

Besides knowledge acquisition, fostering exchange and mutual learning among training participants is another key component of SSHOC trainings. The group settings allow participants to get in touch and work together on issues of mutual concern. Group work is also important for networking and creating synergies between individuals and organisations beyond the training sessions.

Individual work

During the *SSHOC Open Science and Research Data Management Train-the-Trainer Bootcamp at IASSIST 2021* and the *SSHOC Train-the-Trainer RDM Bootcamp Jointly Organised by SSHOC and DARIAH*, participants were given homework assignments related to developing their own training concepts. As attendees often desire more hands-on exercises, homework assignments are a useful tool. Thus, the participants could apply the knowledge they gained from the courses to their own professional context. However, individual learning has been the least used training method during the SSHOC project because individual work (in the form of homework assignments) is only possible when the training activities take place over more than one day.

Training activities

The SSH Training Community is realized through the following activities of SSHOC task 6.4:

Organisation of SSHOC train-the-trainer bootcamps

The SSHOC train-the-trainer bootcamps offered an intense learning opportunity due to the interactive and practice-oriented approach. In close contact with the participants, the bootcamps are designed as hubs for knowledge acquisition and application. Due to the pandemic, the original plans were amended and all bootcamps took place online. The main goal of the train-the-trainer bootcamps was knowledge transfer and networking between SSH trainers, and building skills on topics related to training for open science practices and RDM.

D6.12 provides an overview of all bootcamps, the offered training topics and offers an analysis of best practices and lessons learned for delivering online training events.¹²

Development of the SSH Trainers Directory

The SSH Trainers Directory is a database of trainers in SSH. For a detailed description of the SSH Trainers Directory, see chapter four in this document: [The SSH Trainers Directory](#).

Hosting monthly Training Community Calls

The Training Community Calls are a format for exchange and discussion of diverse topics related to RDM and training. Chapter [3.2 Training Community Calls](#) in this document addresses those monthly online meetings in greater detail.

Implementing the SSH Training Discovery Toolkit¹³

The SSH Training Discovery Toolkit is a virtual resource of training materials across a range of topics including RDM, FAIR data, open science, programming, and didactics in the SSH. For more information, see D6.9 *SSHOC Trainer Toolkit*.¹⁴ An updated version (D6.11) is scheduled for January 2022.

3. The SSH Training Community in Detail

3.1 Overview of the Members

The SSHOC project is a community-led project. Aiming at maximizing its impact and visibility, as well as expanding the user base of its outputs, its target stakeholders need to be given the opportunity to participate in SSHOC-related activities. The *Community Engagement Strategy*¹⁵ (D6.1) set the basis for engagement throughout the whole duration of the SSHOC project. Currently, the Training Community counts 172 members (November 2021).

¹² This list is taken from D6.12, *Report on the Train-the-Trainer Bootcamps*. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5734300> [accessed Nov 2021].

¹³ SSH Training Discovery Toolkit: <https://sshopencloud.eu/ssh-training-discovery-toolkit> [accessed Nov 2021]. There will be a separate deliverable (D6.11) after publishing this deliverable (D6.13).

¹⁴ *SSHOC Trainer Toolkit* (D6.9): <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.3824754> [accessed Nov 2021].

¹⁵ *SSHOC Community Engagement Strategy*: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.3592244> [accessed Nov 2021].

Members' geographic distribution

The 172 members of the Training Community come from various countries across Europe and far beyond. Whereas the majority is located in the European Union, there are also participants from the United States (5), China (2) and Australia (2).

FIGURE 1: GEOGRAPHIC DISTRIBUTION OF SSH TRAINING COMMUNITY MEMBERS

The five most represented countries are Germany, the Netherlands, United Kingdom, France, and Italy.

TABLE 1: TOP FIVE COUNTRIES REPRESENTED WITHIN THE SSH TRAINING COMMUNITY

RANK	COUNTRY	NUMBER OF MEMBERS
1	Germany	17
2	the Netherlands	15
3	United Kingdom	12
4	France	11
5	Italy	10

Members' main academic disciplines

The Training Community benefits from the knowledge of different academic disciplines (Figure 3). The top five most represented disciplines are:

- Sociology (55 members),
- Political Science (45),
- Cultural Heritage and Museology (41),
- Communication Sciences (38)
- Linguistics (36).

FIGURE 2: MAIN ACADEMIC DISCIPLINE OF THE TRAINING COMMUNITY MEMBERS

Stakeholder representation

As illustrated in Figure 3, the SSHOC project is relevant to a wide spectrum of stakeholders. The top three groups that form the user basis of the Training Community belong to these categories:

- Universities and research performing organisations (44 members),

- Research libraries and archives (37),
- Researchers (22).

FIGURE 3: SSHOC STAKEHOLDER REPRESENTATION IN THE TRAINING COMMUNITY

Comparison to the user statistics published in the first report on the Training Network (D6.10)

The first deliverable on the training network (D6.10) was approved by the European Commission in November 2020. User statistics were collected in April of that year.¹⁶ Since then, the SSH Training Community has grown constantly regarding the number of memberships. Whereas the Training Community counted 75 members in April 2020, the number has grown to 172 in November 2021. That is an increase of 229% within the last 1.5 years.

It is noteworthy that this quantitative increase in memberships does not necessarily correlate with a major diversification of the membership base. For example, the distribution between stakeholder categories (Figure 3) has remained relatively the same. That indicates the SSH Training Community has a stable target audience and has continued to attract professionals that are mainly active as researchers (04/2020: 14 members, 11/2021: 22 members), or work at universities and research performing organisations (04/2020: 21 members, 11/2021: 44 members) and research libraries and archives (April

¹⁶ For a detailed view on the SSHOC Training Community user statistics of April 2020, see: SSHOC D6.10 *Report on the SSHOC Training Community*, p.14-16: <https://zenodo.org/record/4558301#.YWA7T2LP2Mq> [accessed Nov 2021].

2020: 24 members, November 2021: 37 members). Those three categories are still at the top with a larger difference to the other ones. There is a special increase in the number of representatives from universities and research performing organisations; that number doubled. Thus, the Training Community is significantly more deeply rooted in those stakeholder categories than 1.5 years ago.

However, the increase in Training Community memberships did result in a diversification of academic disciplines. Whereas the top two ranks remained the same between April 2020 and November 2021 (Sociology and Political Science, see Table 1), there is a—in many cases notable—growth of members from the other disciplines. For example, the number of members from academic disciplines that were barely represented within the SSH Training Community in April 2020 has significantly increased until November 2021. Some examples are: History, Philosophy and Sociology of Sciences (04/2020: 11, 11/2021: 27 members), Education (04/2020: 10, 11/2021: 35 members), and Archaeology and Prehistory (04/2020: 4, 11/2021: 20 members). Thus, the T6.4 organisers managed to broaden the user base of the Training Community with regard to the more diversified representation of academic disciplines.

TABLE 2: TOP FIVE ACADEMIC DISCIPLINES REPRESENTED WITHIN THE SSH TRAINING COMMUNITY

RANK	APRIL 2020 (N=75)	NOVEMBER 2021 (N=172)
1	Sociology (29)	Sociology (55)
2	Political Science (23)	Political Science (45)
3	Communication Sciences (17)	Cultural Heritage and Museology (41)
4	Methods and Statistics (16)	Communication Sciences (38)
5	Linguistics (14)	Linguistics (36)

Feedback from the members of the SSH Training Community

Member satisfaction is important for the SSHOC T6.4 activities design and implementation. That is why the T6.4 team is constantly open for feedback via email. Additionally, participants of formats such as the SSHOC train-the-trainer bootcamps could give feedback directly after the events took place. Furthermore, for the preparation of this report, a survey was created to find out more about which and how often Training Community formats and tools were and are used. The participants were also given the chance to state their motivation for joining the training community and could indicate their preference regarding the sustainability of the Training Community after the end of the SSHOC project. The participation in the survey was not high enough for the results to be considered representative for the experience of the people that are part of the SSH Training Community, hence an analysis is not included. However, this small feedback will be further explored within the T6.4, especially for purposes related to the sustainability of the Community and a potential continuation following SSHOC project.

3.2 Training Community Calls

Training Community Calls have been a part of the Training Community portfolio since March 2020. Until November 2021, 18 Training Community Calls took place.¹⁷ Originally, they were planned on a bi-monthly basis. Due to the pandemic, the calls were extended to a monthly format to stay better connected with the Training Community members in times of mere online communication.

The Training Community Calls covered a variety of topics in the following areas:

- SSHOC tools (SSH Training Discovery Toolkit, SSH Trainers Directory, SSH Marketplace),
- Open Science and RDM-specific topics,
- Best practices for organising online training events,
- Community exchange and networking.

It is noteworthy that the number of participants remained rather constant. Each Training Community Call had around 15 participants, but the composition of the group varied from topic to topic. First, that indicates the formation of expert groups within the community who tend to exchange knowledge and experiences, and network on a regular basis. Second, the different group compositions imply that the T6.4 managed to attract different audiences. Although not every topic seemed to be relevant for each member who followed the activities of Training Community Calls, the variety of topics allowed the representation of different interests among the participants. The variety of topics, consequently, was also reflected in the engagement of various external speakers from different countries and academic disciplines. They gave topic-specific input and inspiration to start discussions—interactivity and input from Training Community members were at the centre of the calls.

4. The SSH Trainers Directory

The SSH Trainers Directory is a database of qualified and experienced trainers in the social sciences and humanities. As of November 2021, it lists 12 user profiles. To strengthen mutual benefits of acquiring knowledge and creating networks, the tool supports trainers in gaining visibility and promoting their training activities. At the same time, it helps event organisers to approach qualified and experienced

¹⁷ A detailed overview of the Training Community Calls, its topics and speakers can be found in the [appendix](#) of this report.

trainers as speakers for their event formats. In that sense, the Trainers Directory supports the creation of a powerful international network of training professionals.

Being a member of the Trainers Directory allows experienced trainers in the fields of the SSH to be visible not only to the SSHOC community but also to a variety of other stakeholders: universities and research performing organisations, research funding institutes, civil society, citizen scientists, policymakers, representatives from the private sector and industry and beyond.

The Trainers Directory was established for anyone interested in finding trainers and their courses in the field of social sciences and humanities. These can for instance be event organisers, who would like to invite a trainer for a session. Based on interests and training needs, a person can use the Trainers Directory to find trainers for a given purpose. Anyone on the internet can see the profile picture (if uploaded), the trainer's name, and domain of expertise. According to their needs, a person can filter the search options to create a list of possible trainers based on the following criteria:

- Topics of expertise
- Target audience
- Spoken languages
- Domain
- Level of training

One can approach a qualified and experienced trainer of their choice by registering on the SSHOC webpage. The registration is needed due to the privacy protection rules and regulations. Therefore, the trainers' personal information is stored in a secure space, available only to registered users.

Members of the Trainers Directory

The SSHOC partners that already are connected through research, software development, surveys, dissemination, and training activities are welcome to become part of a network of professionals through the Trainers Directory. Professional and experienced trainers wishing to be listed in the Trainers Directory outside of the SSHOC project are also invited to become part of the SSH community. The Members of the SSH Training Directory can promote their work, research, and training, increase their visibility, and become part of a recognised professional community. The Trainers Directory database is permanently open to professionals aiming to provide their contribution to research activities and research support in the SSH, to strengthen the community, to support tools and service development in the SSHOC projects and to facilitate the exchange of experiences.

Criteria to be listed in the Trainers Directory

A trainer wishing to be listed in the Trainers Directory needs to fulfil the following criteria:

- Have a qualification as a trainer/teacher's license, or
- Have two years of work experience as a trainer, or

- Have already conducted at least three training activities and provided proof on the Trainers Directory profile webpage.
- Provide a description of three training activities (course outline) including links to the training materials.
- Provide personal information (CV, e-mail).

Voluntary information about the trainers includes:

- Proven knowledge of teaching and presentation techniques, e.g., by participation in a SSHOC train-the-trainer bootcamp and/or a SSHOC workshop.
- Knowledge of adult learning methods.

Required commitment

The duration of the training activities may vary from one hour to several days. This should be indicated in a syllabus for each training activity. A syllabus should include the following information:

- Training structure and practical exercises: Ideally, training activities should consist of a mix of theoretical course lectures and practical exercises. The practical exercises should be supported by training materials, presentations, and tools. Based on experiences, generally, the practical exercises are more critically evaluated by participants.
- Communicate content of a training activity: Trainers wishing to be listed in the directory need to provide information about their training activities, indicated in the course syllabus: course name, description, objectives, duration, target group, level of training, training methods & main activities, expected outcome of the activity, literature used.
- Links to the training materials: At the end of each training activity, trainers are asked to provide links to their training materials. Alternatively, the training materials can be linked to the SSH Training Discovery Toolkit. It is important to also add a list of references to the syllabus, i.e., literature used for the training activities and preparatory readings.

Sustainability

The sustainability of the Trainers Directory is an ongoing process linked to the overall SSHOC sustainability planning, see [5. Sustainability and Future of the SSH Training Community](#).

5. Sustainability and Future of the SSH Training Community

The SSH Training Community supports several activities that could be continued after the end of the SSHOC project (end of April 2022). Therefore, different plans for sustainability are currently being investigated in the framework of the overall SSHOC sustainability planning. The final decision about the future of the SSH Training Community, the Trainers Directory, and the Training Discovery Toolkit, is planned to take place during the last phase of the SSHOC project.

General sustainability

The training activities of T6.4 have resulted in increased collaboration between the trainers and training coordinators. There is a certain overlap in membership between the SSH Training Community and the more generic Community of Practice for Training Coordinators¹⁸, as well as a high level of collaboration, for example, in aligning activities around training catalogues¹⁹ in the SSH such as DARIAH Campus and the SSH Training Discovery Toolkit. Meeting each other in the Training Community Calls has resulted in collaboration around organising the SSHOC train-the-trainer bootcamps.

The Training Community as a community of trainers active in the SSH

All these options on how to deal with the Training Community will be investigated:

1. The Training Community could be part of a potential Memorandum of Understanding of the several SSH ERICs collaborating in the framework of the SSHOC project, towards framing collaboration on some of the shared outputs after the SSHOC project.
2. Elect a small team from the community to become the administrators and maintain the community. These coordinating team members could rotate. Activities could include maintaining the mailing list, setting up monthly calls, or organise one SSH train-the-trainer event per year. This small team effort for coordination could be funded by the research infrastructures mentioned in option one.

¹⁸ This is the official website of the Community of Practice of Training Coordinators: <https://www.openaire.eu/cop-training> [accessed Nov 2021].

¹⁹ An example of cooperation in the field of catalogues is a mutual workshop, organised within the Open Science Fair, September 2021: <https://www.sshopencloud.eu/news/rdm-training-support-catalogue-landscape-reflections-open-science-fair-workshop> [accessed Nov 2021].

3. One of the ERICs could pick up the Training Community as a new activity under its current structure and line of work, thus targeting a broader audience (e.g., CESSDA, within the context of the already existing CESSDA training group).
4. The SSH Training Community could also become a sub-group of the Community of Practice of Training Coordinators, as a trainers' community of practice specific to the SSH. This will be discussed with the Chair and the Co-chair of the CoP of Training Coordinators. It is envisioned to start the dialogue at the beginning of 2022.

Sustainability of individual SSH Training Community components

The train-the-trainer bootcamps

The train-the-trainer bootcamps were organised in a shared effort by partners of the SSHOC project, also inviting the speakers from outside the project that are involved in the Training Community²⁰. The training resources have persistent identifiers and can be found on Zenodo²¹.

The SSH Trainers Directory

The SSH Trainers Directory is part of the SSHOC website and is created to improve the visibility and discoverability of trainers active in SSH. It will be updated and maintained until the end of the project. The experiences in creating the directory have resulted in sharing experiences with the EOSC Future project (October 2021). For the SSH Trainers Directory to be sustained after the SSHOC project there are several options currently being considered:

1. In EOSC Future it is envisioned to create a Trainers Directory as part of the *EOSC Training Catalogue*. The project lead has been contacted to discuss a possible ingestion of the information on trainers that have already subscribed to the SSH Trainers Directory. This would give the SSH trainers more visibility.
2. The SSH Trainers Directory could also be part of a Memorandum of Understanding (see before) between the ERICs.
3. The Trainers Directory could be taken over by one of the ERICs, by the Community of Practice of Training Coordinators, or by other new projects/entities such as TRIPLE/OPERAs.

²⁰ For more information on the organisation of the SSHOC train-the-trainer bootcamps, see: D6.12 *Report on the Train-The-Trainer Bootcamps*: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5734300> [accessed Nov 2021].

²¹ By searching for "SSHOC bootcamps" on www.zenodo.org, the training materials can be accessed.

The SSH Training Discovery Toolkit

Future plans for the SSH Training Discovery Toolkit will be discussed in the upcoming deliverable on the update of the toolkit (D6.11).

6. Conclusion

Building and empowering the SSH Training Community is a significant achievement of the SSHOC Work Package 6. By providing a platform for mutual learning and exchange, the efforts in T6.4 made and continue to make an important contribution to user engagement and training activities of the SSHOC project. Through empowerment of trainers in the SSH, the T6.4 activities are putting them at the core of the SSHOC project.

In that sense, the SSH Training Community is an important instrument to build a bridge between the SSHOC partner organisations and people that use SSHOC tools and services, and at the same time are training others. During the SSHOC project, the community has brought together people from numerous backgrounds and disciplines and facilitated networking and knowledge transfer between a wide range of stakeholders.

This report has illustrated the various elements that build and foster the SSH Training Community. All of them are valuable, as every tool and every format have distinct characteristics that serve different purposes and are relevant for different SSH stakeholders. It is the interplay between the SSHOC partner organisations, in the case of the SSH Training Community mainly the ones engaged in T6.4, and its user community (i.e., trainers in the SSH) that creates the possibility to shaping Europe's digital future. Discussions in the following months will show how the SSH Training Community will continue once the SSHOC project ends.

The train-the-trainer approach facilitated knowledge acquisition and networking activities within the SSH Training Community and will continue to have an impact because community members train their colleagues and people from other organisations. By engaging in a cloud-based infrastructure that encourages open science practices, more and more people will become advocates of open and FAIR research practices in the SSH in the EU and beyond.

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Appendix

Training Community Calls – An overview

Duration: 1 hour / call

In this overview of the calls only one out of the four SSHOC train-the-trainer bootcamps is included as this bootcamp was organised exclusively for the SSH Training Community. All train-the-trainer bootcamps are summarised in a separate report.²²

The Training Community members have exclusive access to the online Training Community workspace where all the meeting materials (such as presentations and discussion notes) are available.

TABLE 3: OVERVIEW OF SSH TRAINING COMMUNITY CALLS

Date	Type	Topic	Speakers
2020			
19-03-2020	Community Call	Kick-off	LIBER DANS
07-05-2020	Community Call	Toolkit sneak peek + year plan	LIBER DANS
02-06-2020	Call for Mini-Bootcamp Participants (2 hours)	Training Toolkit (Demo, exercise, content, feedback)	LIBER DANS
09-06-2020	Community Call	Improving online meetings, presentations, and workshops	DANS LIBER
02-07-2020	Community Call	Online and offline games	DANS Valerie McCutcheon (University of Glasgow)
25-08-2020	Community Call	Networking – Speed dating	DANS LIBER
15-09-2020	Community Call	Open Science	Francesca Di Donato (CNR-ILC)

²² See D6.12, *Report on the Train-the-Trainer Bootcamps*. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5734300> [accessed Nov 2021].

			Elena Giglia (University of Turin) Natalia Gruenpeter (University of Warsaw)
15-10-2020	Community Call	SSHOC Trainers Directory - FOSTER example and our wishes	LIBER Iryna Kuchma (EIFL)
10-11-2020	Community Call	Online meetings	GESIS, LIBER, DANS, JHON, ADP
10-12-2020	Community Call	Christmas speed dating, networking	DANS
2021			
11-02-2021	Community Call	Lessons learned: Organising a large event online	LIBER CESSDA/UL-ADP, Trust-IT, DANS/FREYA
09-03-2021	Community Call	Reuse of training materials	DANS Mateuz Kuzak (The Netherlands e-Science Center)
13-04-2021	Community Call combined with the CoP of training coordinators call	SSH Training Community	LIBER DANS
18-05-2021	Community Call	Checklist for Zoom meetings	LIBER DANS GESIS
06-07-2021	Community Call	SSH Training Directory	GESIS LIBER Trust-IT
16-09-2021	Community Call	Helsinki Hackathon	Eetu Mäkelä, Associate Professor in Human Science
07-10-2021	Community Call	RDA Minimal metadata for training resources	Elizabeth Newbold (STFC)
11-11-2021	Community Call	Co-organised Hybrid Conference: Conference on Computer-Mediated Communication	Lieke Verheijen (Radboud University)
16-12-2021	Community Call	Christmas Edition	